

APPLICATION OF A TRANSFORMER CONVERTER WITH A DISCRETE OUTPUT IN AN AUTOMATIC CONTROL SYSTEM .

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Abstract: *based on the analysis of scientific and technical literature, the question of the use of transformer mechanical voltage converters with a discrete output in the automatic control system in critical production work is considered , which will allow, when used, to reduce the likelihood of accidents during repair work.*

Keywords : *transformer converter of mechanical stresses, automatic control system, sensor, digital code, control unit, discrete output, blocking, converter, indicator, digital-to-analog, main pipeline.*

At present, transformer converters of mechanical stresses have found their application for non-contact conversion of existing mechanical stresses in critical parts of machines and mechanisms into an electrical signal. Mechanical stress converters are used in measuring instruments, control systems, as well as various automatic blocking devices.

Discrete systems differ from continuous ones in that among the signals acting in the system there are discrete signals. Discrete signals are obtained from continuous ones by quantization in terms of level, in terms of time, or both in terms of level and time. Systems in the structure of which digital devices, controllers, microprocessors, computers are used are discrete. When carrying out repairs on main pipelines, according to the technology, the pipeline is lifted from the trench to a height at which the theoretically calculated mechanical stresses in the pipeline do not exceed the proportionality limit. However , due to metal corrosion, thinning of the pipeline walls is observed, which leads to a high

concentration of mechanical stresses in the pipeline material, and sometimes to emergency situations.

From the analysis of various designs of transformer converters of mechanical stresses, it can be concluded that, regardless of the design features of the converters, information is converted in them in three physical circuits, namely: mechanical, magnetic and electrical. To simplify the analysis, calculation and synthesis of circuits of various physical nature, it is convenient to use a single mathematical apparatus that uses the principle of direct analogy, i.e. as generalized quantities characterizing the processes for the purposes of any physical nature of transformer converters of mechanical stresses, the magnitude of the impact is taken - the generalized voltage U , the magnitude of the reaction - the generalized current I and charge q [1].

The possibility of using transformer transducers of mechanical stresses for converting mechanical stresses in pipe steels was shown in [2], however, the transducers used had low metrological characteristics.

From the analysis of works devoted to transformer converters of mechanical stresses used in the automatic control system, we can formulate the following requirements for converters:

- high sensitivity to mechanical stresses;
- small conversion error;
- high speed;
- the possibility of processing the signals of the converter with the help of a computer;
- the possibility of transforming the components of a complex stress state;
- manufacturability and ease of operation;
- low cost and high reliability [3].

An analysis of the designs of transformer mechanical stress converters showed that both converters implement a method for converting mechanical stresses, which can be formulated as follows. To reduce the error in the conversion of mechanical stresses from changes in the air gap, it is necessary to make two measurements of

the output value of the transformer mechanical stress converters at two values of the magnetic conductivity of the air gap, which are changed by changing the converter or the initial air gap. However, these designs have several disadvantages. Therefore, a transformer converter of mechanical stresses was developed, in which the change in the magnetic conductivity of the air gap is carried out by changing the effective cross-sectional area of the poles of the magnetic circuit [four].

Efficient and reliable automatic control systems (ACS) for various industrial installations and technological processes can only be created on the basis of efficient and reliable automation tools, among which the converters of various parameters of these processes are the first. The use of digital computers in ACS posed to the developers the problem of pairing the computer with the means of information perception. In this connection, there was a great practical need for the development of primary converters with a code or digital output.

From the analysis of various designs of transformer converters of mechanical stresses, it can be concluded that, regardless of the design features of the converters, they convert information in three physical circuits, namely: mechanical, magnetic and electrical [5].

When developing a method for calculating a transformer mechanical stress converter (TMC) with a discrete output, the initial equation is a statistical characteristic, which is necessary, first of all, to determine the optimal ratio of the geometric parameters of the magnetic circuit, the number of windings and the optimal operating mode of the converter. As criteria for optimizing the parameters of the transducer, the following are usually used: maximum sensitivity, minimum error and maximum speed [6].

For to prevent pipeline breakdowns during their overhaul, a control system was developed, including changing, recording the existing mechanical stresses in the pipeline and blocking the pipeline lifting, the block diagram of which is shown in the figure [7].

Structural diagram of the automatic lifting control system pipeline during its overhaul.

- 1- mechanical stress converter PMN-3M;
- 2- indicator;
- 3- central control point (digital printing);
- 4- Control block;
- 5- actuating mechanism;
- 6- pipelayer [8].

The principle of operation of the system is as follows. From the mechanical stress converter 1, which was used as the PMN-3M brand converters, a digital code is sent proportional to the value of mechanical stresses to the indicator 2, digital printing 3, and also to the comparison unit, in which a comparison is made with the code embedded in the control unit 4. If the values of the codes are equal, the actuator 5 gives sound or light signals, and after digital-to-analogue conversion and amplification, it blocks the lifting device of the pipelayer [9].

The PMN-3M sensors are located on the ring evenly along the circumference at 6 points and move along the pipeline together with the pipelayer trolley . The electronic part of the converter PMN-3M is structurally made of two blocks. The quadratic current pulse generator and the analog part of the converter are located in close proximity to the transformer converter of mechanical stresses and are located on the trolley ring. The computing and matching devices of the converter are located in the cab of the pipelayer [10].

The system showed that the accuracy and dynamic characteristics of the developed transducers meet the requirements of this control system, and also that, most often, mechanical stresses exceed the permissible level in the lower part of the pipeline, which indicates a more intensive thinning of the pipeline walls and reduces the number of sensors used. or distribute them unevenly around the circumference of the pipeline.

The use of the described system made it possible to reduce the likelihood of breakdowns of operating pipelines during their overhaul [11].

From this, drawing a conclusion, we find that the accuracy and speed of the designs of mechanical stress converters with a discrete output are two times higher compared to known converters. Also, they meet the requirements of the automatic control system for lifting and maintaining the main pipeline, and when used in this control system, reduce the likelihood of accidents during the overhaul of main pipelines.

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